

Validation of a Neutronics Solver Using MCNP6 of Multi-Physics Burnup Calculation Code System COMPASS Through Isotopic Composition Analysis of a BWR 9x9 Fuel Assembly

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803813

ABSTRACT

The Central Research Institute of Electric Power Industry (CRIEPI) is developing COMPASS, a comprehensive burnup calculation system designed for large-scale analyses involving numerous meshes and coupled burnup, neutronics, thermal-hydraulics (T/H), and mechanical calculations such as thermal expansion to estimate the core behavior during burnup. COMPASS is based on a modular architecture that incorporates existing calculation codes as external solvers. The current version comprises a control module and three calculation modules: burnup, neutronics, and T/H. In a recent study, MCNP6.3 was implemented in COMPASS as an external neutronics solver. To validate the neutronics and burnup modules, this study performed an isotopic composition analysis of the BWR 9x9 fuel assemblies 2F1ZN2 and 2F1ZN3 from the SFCOMPO2.0 database. Burnup calculations were carried out using COMPASS, which automatically generates MCNP6.3 input files and executes the calculations. Although discrepancies were observed for certain isotopes, such as ²³⁴U, owing to specification deficiencies, the results obtained with JENDL-4.0u1 exhibited accuracy and trends comparable to those reported in previous studies. For the JENDL-5 results, updates from JENDL-4.0u1 in cross-sections and fission yields for some isotopes, such as ²³⁵U, ²³⁸Pu, and ²⁴²Pu, were confirmed to affect their number densities and those of nearby isotopes. Overall, the isotopic composition analysis of the BWR 9x9 fuel assembly confirms the accuracy of the COMPASS neutronics solver.

Keywords: Burnup Calculation, Isotopic Composition Analysis, COMPASS, MCNP6, Verification & Validation

1. INTRODUCTION

Accurate prediction of spent nuclear fuel isotopic compositions requires tracking calculations that properly consider operating conditions, such as thermal power, fuel and coolant temperatures, and boron concentration. Achieving high accuracy necessitates burnup as well as coupled calculations such as neutronics and thermal-hydraulics (T/H) ones. In addition, high-fidelity geometric modeling is required. In recent years, several studies have reported examples of neutronics and T/H (N-T/H) coupling calculations using high-accuracy code systems, indicating the growing demand for N-T/H coupling analyses [1-4].

The Central Research Institute of Electric Power Industry (CRIEPI) has been developing a comprehensive burnup calculation system, COMPASS, for large-scale analyses and coupled calculations [5-11]. The current version of COMPASS comprises burnup, neutronics, and thermal-hydraulics modules. The ultimate aim is to build an integrated multi-physics burnup calculation system that incorporates burnup-related physical phenomena, including fuel composition, power distribution,

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temperature variations in the fuel, cladding and coolant, as well as thermal expansion and irradiation-induced deformation of fuel and cladding.

In a recent study, MCNP6 was implemented as an external neutronics solver in COMPASS [12]. In this paper, an isotopic composition analysis of a BWR 9x9 fuel assembly is presented to validate this solver.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 outlines the COMPASS code system. Section 3 presents the isotopic composition analysis of the BWR 9x9 fuel assembly, and Section 4 concludes the paper.

2. COMPASS: MULTI-PHYSICS BURNUP CALCULATION CODE SYSTEM

2.1. Outline of COMPASS Code [9]

Figure 1 shows a conceptual diagram of COMPASS. The shaded and translucent areas in Figure 1 indicate the functions under development. The current version of COMPASS includes a control module and three physics modules: burnup, neutronics, and T/H module. The neutronics module solves the neutron transport equation to obtain the neutron flux and reaction rates, such as fission and capture reactions. The burnup module estimates variations in material composition caused by decay and production through nuclear reactions by solving the burnup equation. The T/H module calculates the temperatures of the fuel, cladding, and coolant, as well as coolant properties such as enthalpy and velocity. The control module regulates the entire code system and administers common data, such as geometry. Each module receives the necessary data, such as the thermal power history for the burnup module, via the control module and returns the values estimated by solving its governing equations. The control module manages the returned values, such as the material composition in the burnup module, thermal power in the neutronics module, and material temperature in the T/H module, and transfers them to other modules. This is repeated for each iteration of the coupling calculations, such as N-T/H, to advance the burnup calculation. These calculations are conducted under static (steady-state) conditions because COMPASS targets long timescales, such as a burnup calculation for an operating cycle.

The control and burnup modules are the original modules of COMPASS. The neutronics and T/H modules implement an interface between the data filter and external module using the existing calculation code as an external solver. The T/H module implements the original solver (a one-dimensional T/H solver with fuel rod geometry). Users can use multiple code combinations with a single common input file and receive output files in a standard format along with summary files that organize the calculation results. In addition, COMPASS includes a database of constants, such as atomic masses and natural abundances, which aids in avoiding errors in the calculation results owing to differences in calculation conditions, such as constants used in code-to-code comparisons. In the future, by increasing the choice of calculation codes as external solvers, COMPASS can support options ranging from high-cost but highly accurate computations, such as Monte Carlo transport and computational fluid dynamics (CFD) calculations, to low-cost calculations that provide simple results.

2.2. Implementation of a New Neutronics Solver Using MCNP6

The neutronics module uses existing codes as external solvers: the continuous-energy Monte Carlo code MVP [13] and deterministic calculation code MOSRA-SRAC [14], both developed by the Japan Atomic Energy Agency (JAEA). However, only the pin-cell geometry model can be calculated when using MOSRA-SRAC. By using existing codes as external solvers, their functionality can be efficiently leveraged in COMPASS. For example, the nuclear data libraries available for these codes (i.e., JENDL-5 [15] and ENDF-B/VIII [16]) can be used directly in COMPASS. When new libraries are released, they are incorporated into COMPASS simultaneously with updates to the existing codes.

In a recent study, MCNP6.3, which is an external neutronics solver, was implemented in COMPASS [12]. The MCNP code has been extensively verified and validated and is used worldwide. By utilizing the continuous-energy Monte Carlo method, the MCNP code can solve complex geometries with high accuracy and fidelity, as it avoids the approximation methods commonly used in deterministic

calculations, such as spatial and energy discretization, diffusion approximation, and spatial homogenization. In addition, high computational performance is expected in large-scale computing, such as whole-core calculations, as MCNP6.3 supports both Open Multi-Processing (OpenMP) and a Message Passing Interface (MPI) for parallel computing.

Figure 1. Conceptual diagram of the multi-physics burnup calculation code system COMPASS.

3. ISOTOPIC COMPOSITION ANALYSIS OF BWR 9x9 FUEL ASSEMBLY

Isotopic composition analysis is an effective method for validating burnup calculation code systems. This study focused on the isotopic composition analysis of the BWR 9x9 fuel assemblies 2F1ZN2 and 2F1ZN3 included in the SFCOMPO2.0 database [17]. The assemblies were part of the lead-use 9x9 fuel assemblies and were loaded into Unit 1 of the Fukushima Daini Nuclear Power Plant (2F1) as part of a fresh fuel assembly in December 1996. After three cycles of irradiation, one assembly (2F1ZN2) was discharged in May 2000, and after five cycles of irradiation, another (2F1ZN3) was discharged in January 2003 for post-irradiation examination. Isotopic composition measurements were performed at the JAEA facilities as part of a research project of the Japan Nuclear Energy Safety Organization (JNES). The measured composition data included U, Pu, Nd, Mo, Tc, Ru, Rh, Ag, Cs, Pm, Sm, Eu, and Gd isotopes. The original analysis was conducted by JNES using the Continuous-Energy Monte Carlo Burn-up Code MVP-BURN [18], latest library JENDL-4.0 [19], and burnup chain data ChainJ40 [20], as reported in Ref. [21].

3.1. Calculation Conditions

Figure 2 shows the enrichment distribution in the assemblies and the locations of the fuel rods from which the samples were taken at three measurement points. Among the measurement data contained in the SFCOMPO2.0 database, two samples from 2F1ZN2 (c2: $\text{UO}_2\text{-Gd}_2\text{O}_3$ fuel and c3: UO_2 fuel) targeted the upper axial node, whereas three samples of 2F1ZN3 (c2: $\text{UO}_2\text{-Gd}_2\text{O}_3$ fuel, c3: UO_2 fuel, and a9: UO_2 fuel) targeted the middle node. The differences in the target nodes resulted in differences in the void ratio of the moderator material, which affected the isotopic composition. The original study in Ref. [21] exactly modeled the fuel assembly geometry, including the rounded corners of the channel box.

However, because this information was not included in the SFCOMPO2.0 database, it was not used in this study. Therefore, the measurement results for a9 fuel in the 2F1ZN3 fuel assembly were excluded from the comparison in this study.

COMPASS was performed for the burnup calculation using MCNP6.3 as the external solver of the neutronics calculation module. Neutronics analysis was conducted using a two-dimensional model of the fuel assembly geometry. The targeted fuel pellets, c2, c3, and a9, each had 10 radial regions of equal volume. The ACE format libraries were generated using FREN DYv2 [22] from the nuclear data libraries JENDL-4.0u1 and JENDL-5 [15]. The number of neutron histories per batch was 10,000, and the number of batches was 1100 at each burnup step, with the initial 100 batches skipped in the statistical processing of the multiplication factor. For the burnup calculations, the burnup steps were set to less than 1.5 GWd/t, and the predictor-corrector method was used at each step. The Chebyshev Rational Approximation Method using Incomplete Partial Fraction (CRAM-IPF) [23], burnup solver, and a general burnup chain model, ChainJ40, based on JENDL-4.0 (ChainJ40) [20] were used. The irradiation histories of the assembly power and in-channel void fractions of the relevant axial nodes were obtained using SFCOMPO2.0. The fuel temperature was maintained at 900 K, and the cladding and coolant temperatures were maintained constant at 559 K throughout the burnup calculation.

Figure 2. Calculation model of the BWR 9x9 fuel assembly.

Table I. Comparison of sample burnup between measured and calculated values.

		Measurement value [21]	Burnup [GWd/t]	
			COMPASS/MCNP + JENDL-4.0	COMPASS/MCNP + JENDL-5
ZN2	c2	27.89	27.89	27.85
	c3	38.15	38.14	38.26
ZN3	c2	54.45	54.47	54.49
	c3	68.42	68.42	68.58

3.2. Calculation Results and Discussions

Table 1 compares the measured and calculated values of the sample burnup. All the calculated sample burnups were consistent with the measured value within 0.2 GWd/t. Figures 3, 4, 5, and 6 compare the isotopic compositions between the calculated results and measured values (C/E-1) for ZN2c2, ZN2c3, ZN3c2, and ZN3c3, respectively. The error bars in the figures indicate measurement-related errors. For the ^{234}U isotope, a significant discrepancy was observed between the calculated results and measured value, which was caused by the SFCOMPO2.0 specification that does not include the initial ^{234}U composition. For ^{156}Gd , ^{157}Gd , and ^{158}Gd isotopes, a significant difference was observed between the results of a previous study [21] and the calculation results with JENDL-4.0, which was caused by the increase in the thermal capture cross section of ^{156}Eu . However, this difference was resolved by modifying the thermal capture cross section for ^{156}Eu in JENDL-4.0 update 1 [24]. Therefore, the differences between the MVP-BURN and COMPASS/MCNP are reasonable.

3.2.1. Comparison of JENDL-4.0u1 results and measurement values

Although the difference for ^{241}Pu in the ZN2c2 fuel was slightly large, the calculation results of COMPASS using JENDL-4.0u1 for the U, Pu, and Nd isotopes in the three-cycle irradiated fuel (Figures 3 and 4) reproduced the measured values within a 10% range. The fission products (FPs), except for ^{156}Gd , ^{157}Gd , and ^{158}Gd , also showed a trend similar to that observed in the calculation results of a previous study [21]. The calculated values for the ^{235}U and Pu isotopes were overestimated compared to the measured values. This was because of the absence of ^{234}U in the initial composition, resulting in a higher initial composition of ^{238}U , which in turn increased ^{238}U capture reactions and Pu isotope production. The calculation results for the U and Pu isotopes in the five-cycle irradiated fuel (Figures 5 and 6) further emphasized the differences observed in the three-cycle irradiated fuel. As the measurement target was UO_2 fuel, all Pu isotope production was attributable to the capture and (n, 2n) reactions of U isotopes. Both ^{235}U for the ZN3c2 and ZN3c3 fuels were overestimated by several percent compared with the measured values. From the overestimated ^{235}U , the increase in Pu isotopes owing to an overestimation of U isotope capture reactions and the resulting change in the fission reaction ratio between U and Pu isotopes were predicted to have contributed to this effect. However, further investigation is required to verify this.

3.2.2. Comparison of JENDL-4.0u1 and JENDL-5 results

The ^{238}Pu number densities of JENDL-5 for all samples were predicted to be lower than those of JENDL-4.0u1. This is due to the increase in the (n, γ) reaction cross section in the thermal and resonance regions of JENDL-5 compared with JENDL-4.0u1. The Sm isotopes differed significantly between JENDL-4.0u1 and JENDL-5, although the (n, γ) and (n, 2n) reaction cross sections of JENDL-4.0u1 and JENDL-5 were comparable. However, the fission yields of ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu , as the major fission reaction sources, were modified. The production of Sm isotopes has been estimated to change according to the modifications of these fission yields. A comparison of the burnup calculation results for the JENDL-4.0 and JENDL-5 with a focus on PWR fuel assembly is reported in Ref. [25]. A similar trend was observed in the present study.

For all samples, the results for ^{235}U of JENDL-5 were predicted to be lower than the JENDL-4.0u1 results because of the modification of the fission and (n, γ) reaction cross section of ^{235}U for JENDL-5. The results for ^{151}Eu from JENDL-5 were closer to the measured values than those from JENDL-4.0u1. The (n, γ) reaction cross section of ^{151}Eu for JENDL-5 increased in the thermal and resonance regions compared with that in JENDL-4.0u1. This indicates a decreasing number density of ^{151}Eu owing to an increase in the $^{151}\text{Eu}(n, \gamma)^{152}\text{Eu}$ reaction.

Figure 3. Comparison of isotopic composition between calculated and measured values in ZN2c2 sample (three-cycle, UO₂-Gd₂O₃ fuel).

Figure 4. Comparison of isotopic composition between calculated and measured values in ZN2c3 sample (three-cycle, UO₂ fuel).

Figure 5. Comparison of isotopic composition between calculated and measured values in ZN3c2 sample (five-cycle, UO₂-Gd₂O₃ fuel).

Figure 6. Comparison of isotopic composition between calculated and measured values in ZN2c3 sample (five-cycle, UO₂ fuel).

4. CONCLUSIONS

For large-scale analyses involving numerous meshes and coupled calculations of burnup, neutronics, T/H, mechanics such as thermal expansion and irradiation-induced deformation, CRIEPI has developed a comprehensive burnup calculation system called COMPASS. The COMPASS framework was designed to use existing computer codes as external solvers. As a new feature, MCNP6.3, an external neutronics solver, was implemented in COMPASS. This function is expected to achieve high computational performance in large-scale computing, such as whole-core calculations.

An isotopic composition analysis was conducted to validate the neutronics and burnup calculation code system, excluding T/H calculations, using BWR 9x9 fuel assemblies 2F1ZN2 and 2F1ZN3 from the SFCOMPO2.0 database. COMPASS calculations were performed with MCNP6.3 as the external solver of the neutronics calculation module, with the nuclear data libraries JENDL-4.0 and JENDL-5. Through isotopic composition analysis of the targeted three- and five-cycle irradiated BWR 9x9 fuel assemblies containing UO₂-Gd₂O₃ fuel, the calculation accuracy of the COMPASS neutronics solver using MCNP6.3 was confirmed. The U, Pu, and Nd isotopes for the three-cycle fuel agree with the measured values within a range of approximately 10% and the five-cycle fuel also agree within 15%. Regarding the differences between JENDL-4.0u1 and JENDL-5, trends consistent with those reported in a previous study were observed, reflecting changes in cross sections and fission yields for certain isotopes, such as ²³⁵U, ²³⁸Pu, and ²⁴²Pu, were confirmed.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Collins, A. Godfrey, "Analysis of the BEAVRS Benchmark using VERA-CS" *Proceedings of Joint International Conference on Mathematics and Computation (M&C), Supercomputing in Nuclear Applications (SNA) and the Monte Carlo (MC) Method (ANS MC2015)*, Nashville, TN, USA (2015).
- [2] B. Collins, A. Godfrey, S. Stimpson, S. Palmtag, "Simulation of the BEAVRS Benchmark using VERA" *Proceedings of International Conference on Mathematics & Computational Methods Applied to Nuclear Science & Engineering (M&C2017)*, Jeju, Korea (2017).
- [3] K. Wang, S. Liu, Z. Li, et al., "Analysis of BEAVRS two-cycle benchmark using RMC based on full core detailed model", *Prog. Nucl. Energy* **98**, pp. 301-312 (2017).
- [4] J. Yu, H. Lee, H. Kim, et al., "Simulations of BEAVRS benchmark cycle 2 depletion with MCS/CTF coupling system", *Nucl. Eng. Tech.* **52**, pp. 661-673 (2020).
- [5] M. Suzuki, "A Development of Multi-Physics Burnup Analysis System (1) An Overall Plan and Implementation of Burnup Calculation Module" *Proceedings of 2021 Annual Meeting on Atomic Energy Society of Japan*, pp. 1B04, Online, Japan (2021). [in Japanese].
- [6] M. Suzuki, "A Development of Multi-Physics Burnup Analysis System (2) Implementation of Burnup Analysis Function with Fuel Assembly Geometry" *Proceedings of 2022 Annual Meeting on Atomic Energy Society of Japan*, pp. 2D03, Online, Japan (2022). [in Japanese].

- [7] M. Suzuki, S. Sato, "A Development of Multi-Physics Burnup Analysis System (3) Burnup Calculation Applying Exact Resonance Elastic Scattering model" *Proceedings of 2022 Annual Meeting on Atomic Energy Society of Japan*, pp. 2D04, Online, Japan (2022). [in Japanese].
- [8] M. Suzuki, K. Inagaki, S. Sato, S. Kitajima, "A Development of Multi-Physics Burnup Analysis System (4) Implementation of Thermal-Hydraulics Calculation Function" *Proceedings of 2022 Fall Meeting on Atomic Energy Society of Japan*, pp. 1F02, Hitachi, Ibaraki, Japan (2022). [in Japanese].
- [9] M. Suzuki, "Development of a Multi-Physics Burnup Code System: COMPASS" *Proceedings of The International Conference on Mathematics and Computational Methods Applied to Nuclear Science and Engineering (M&C 2023)*, Niagara Falls, Ontario, Canada (2023).
- [10] M. Suzuki, "A Development of Multi-Physics Burnup Analysis System (5) Implementation of Interpolation Function for Material Temperature using Pseudo Material Method" *Proceedings of 2023 Fall Meeting on Atomic Energy Society of Japan*, pp. 1M11, Nagoya, Aichi, Japan (2023). [in Japanese].
- [11] M. Suzuki, "A Development of Multi-Physics Burnup Analysis System (6) Implementation of Interpolation Function of Cross Section for Material Temperature using Pseudo Material Method (Part 2)" *Proceedings of 2024 Annual Meeting on Atomic Energy Society of Japan*, pp. 2L12, Hitachi, Ibaraki, Japan (2024). [in Japanese].
- [12] K. Mori, M. Suzuki "A Development of Multi-Physics Burnup Analysis System (7) Implementation of MCNP6 as Additional Neutronics Calculation Solver" *Proceedings of 2025 Annual Meeting on Atomic Energy Society of Japan*, pp. 2D01, Kumamoto, Kumamoto, Japan (2025). [in Japanese].
- [13] Y. Nagaya, K. Okumura, T. Sakurai and T. Mori, *MVP/GMVP Version 3: General Purpose Monte Carlo Codes for Neutron and Photon Transport Calculations Based on Continuous Energy and Multigroup Methods*, JAEA-Data/Code 2016-018, Japan Atomic Energy Agency, Tokai-mura, Naka-gun, Ibaraki-ken, Japan (2017). URL <https://jopss.jaea.go.jp/pdfdata/JAEA-Data-Code-2016-018.pdf>
- [14] K. Okumura, *MOSRA-SRAC: Lattice Calculation Module of the Modular Code System for Nuclear Reactor Analyses MOSRA*, JAEA-Data/Code 2015-015, Japan Atomic Energy Agency, Tokai-mura, Naka-gun, Ibaraki-ken, Japan (2015). URL <https://jopss.jaea.go.jp/pdfdata/JAEA-Data-Code-2015-015.pdf>
- [15] O. Iwamoto, N. Iwamoto, S. Kunieda, et al., "Japanese Evaluated Nuclear Data Library Version5: JENDL-5" *J. Nucl. Sci. Technol.* **60**[1], pp. 1-60 (2023).
- [16] D.A. Brown, M.B. Chadwick, R. Capote, et al., "ENDF/B-VIII.0: The 8th Major Release of the Nuclear Reaction Data Library with CIELO-project Cross Sections, New Standards and Thermal Scattering Data", *Nuclear Data Sheets* **148**, pp. 1-142 (2018).
- [17] F. Michel-Sendis, I. Gauld, J.S. Martinez, et al., "SFCOMPO-2.0: An OECD NEA database of Spent Nuclear Fuel Isotopic Assays, Reactor Design Specifications, and Operating Data", *Annals of Nuclear Energy* **110**, pp.779-788 (2017).
- [18] K. Okumura, T. Mori, M. Nakagawa and K. Kaneko, "Validation of a Continuous-Energy Monte Carlo Burn-up Code MVP-BURN and Its Application to Analysis of Post Irradiation Experiment" *J. Nucl. Sci. Technol.* **37**[2], pp. 128-138 (2000).
- [19] K. Shibata, O. Iwamoto, T. Nakagawa et al., "JENDL-4.0: A New Library for Nuclear Science and Engineering" *J. Nucl. Sci. Technol.* **48**[1], pp. 1-30 (2011).
- [20] K. Okumura, K. Kojima, T. Okamoto, "Development of the Burn-up Chain Data ChainJ40 based on JENDL-4.0" *Proceedings of 2012 Annual Meeting on Atomic Energy Society of Japan*, pp. 202, Fukui, Fukui, Japan. [in Japanese].
- [21] M. Suzuki, T. Yamamoto, H. Fukaya, et al., "Lattice Physics Analysis of Measured Isotopic Compositions of irradiated BWR 9x9 UO₂ fuel" *J. Nucl. Sci. Technol.* **50**[12], pp. 1161-1176 (2013).
- [22] K. Tada, A. Yamamoto, S. Kunieda, et al., "Development and verification of Nuclear Data Processing Code FRENDY version 2" *J. Nucl. Sci. Technol.* **61**[6], pp. 830-839 (2024).
- [23] M. Pusa, "Higher-Order Chebyshev Rational Approximation Method and Application to Burnup Equations" *Nucl. Sci. Eng.* **182**, pp. 297-318 (2016).
- [24] "JENDL-4.0u & JENDL4.0+" (2012). URL <https://www.ndc.jaea.go.jp/jendl/j40/update/>
- [25] T. Watanabe, K. Tada, T. Endo and A. Yamamoto, "Impact of Nuclear Data Revised from JENDL-4.0 to JENDL-5 on PWR Spent Fuel Nuclide Composition" *J. Nucl. Sci. Technol.* **60**[11], pp. 1386-1396 (2023).